

GIS – BASED APPROACH TO IMPROVE THE RESILIENCE OF THE DISTRIBUTION NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

The subject addressed in this work is the role of resilience in planning distribution networks. Resilience understood as the ability to anticipate, operate, and learn from disruptive events, is emerging as a fundamental principle in the planning and operation of networks. This work introduces a GIS-based approach to tackle the issue of resilience in network planning. The specific circumstances notably influence the disruptive events that may affect the network. Therefore, a resilience approach must effectively manage both the system's technical characteristics and the particularities of its location. Geographical Information Systems (GIS) allow the management and analysis of large amounts of geolocated data. The GIS-based approach proposed in this work addresses the system's resilience considering hazards, defined as disruptive events that may impact the infrastructure without being controllable, and vulnerabilities, described as infrastructure weaknesses characterized by their likelihood of occurrence when a hazard is present and the potential impact they may cause.

INTRODUCTION

Resilience has become a fundamental concept in power systems. In 2012, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published a Special Report to manage the risks that might arise due to extreme weather conditions [1]. Resilience is defined as "the ability of a system and its component parts to anticipate, absorb, accommodate, or recover from the effects of a hazardous event in a timely and efficient manner, including through the preservation, restoration, or improvement of its essential basic structures and functions". The report also recognizes the vulnerabilities of the power systems and how this might impact keeping the supply to all consumers.

In that context, in 2015, the European Joint Research Center (JRC) published the report *Building a Resilient Europe in a Globalised World* [2]. The report addresses the necessity of an interdisciplinary approach to building a resilient European Union (EU). In 2020, the "2020 Strategic Foresight Report" was published [3] introducing resilience as a new concept for EU policies. Later, Regulation (EU) 2021/241 [4] and Regulation (EU) 2023/43 [5] introduced some measures to address the European recovery after COVID-19 and the Ukraine's war crisis. In these regulations, the resilience of the transmission and distribution networks is identified as a crucial element to guarantee system flexibility, minimize congestion, and ensure supply chains, among others.

In the US, the Department of Energy is focused on the modernization and expansion of the electricity grid to integrate renewable energies while increasing resilience [6]. In this line, the US Department of Energy's National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) defines resilience as "The ability to anticipate, prepare for, and adapt to changing conditions and withstand, respond to, and recover rapidly from disruptions through adaptable and holistic planning and technical solutions" [7].

Considering the importance of resilience in power systems [8] proposes a specific definition and quantification methods of resilience in power systems. The authors distinguish between two-time horizons: operational or short-term and infrastructural or long-term. In both horizons, resilience is linked to risk-based approaches to evaluate both the potential disruptive events and the weaknesses of the infrastructure.

This work proposes a GIS-based approach to assess the resilience of planning power systems. Thus, the authors identified GIS as a promising system for managing the information related to networks. The proposed methodology relies on the framework developed by NREL [9], which stems from a comprehensive risk assessment. Thus, this work discerns between hazards and vulnerabilities. Disruptive events that may impact the infrastructure without being controllable define hazards. In turn, weaknesses relate to vulnerabilities and are determined by their likelihood of occurrence when a hazard is present and the potential impact they may cause. A GIS system effectively manages multiple layers of information, providing a realistic representation of the system's characteristics and potential hazards.

Finally, as an example, this paper analyzes a network located in a rural area in Spain using the proposed GIS-based approach, thereby demonstrating the methodology's potential.

METHODOLOGY

This section describes the GIS-based methodology proposed to evaluate the network's resilience, which is summarized in Figure 2 and described along the following subsections.

The following terms are used to describe the methodology:

- **LAYER:** Visual geospatial data representation within a digital mapping environment. Each layer is a vector of features.
- **FEATURE:** Any area or element of the Earth's surface that can be represented on a map. Features are,

mainly, points, lines and polygons. Apart from its geographic representation, features can include additional information about the elements. The additional information is defined through attributes.

- **ATTRIBUTES:** Nonspatial properties of a feature. Attributes are characterized by **FIELD** and **VALUE**. The **FIELD** is the name of the property and the **VALUE** the property itself. **VALUE** can include numerical, alphanumeric, or descriptive information.
- **TABULAR DATA:** Nonspatial descriptive information stored in rows and columns. Tabular data can be joined to spatial data. Each row would be linked to a feature and each column would be an attribute. The column name would correspond to the attribute's field and each row value's to each attribute's value.

Hazards

This section describes the procedure for building the hazard database, symbolized by **H**. The hazard database **H** is a set of layers defined as $\mathbf{H} = [h_1, h_2, \dots, h_m, \dots, h_M]$ where h_m represents a layer that defines a hazard included in the database and M the total number of layers of the set. Each layer includes the necessary features to characterize the hazard in a certain region. Four attributes are expected in each layer that would define the probability of occurrence in each year's season.

Figure 1 describes the database development process. First, hazards that might affect an electrical system should be compiled and included in **H**. Second, an iterative process is required to identify all hazards that might occur simultaneously. Once two potential simultaneous hazards are identified the combined probability should be determined based on the relation between the hazards:

- $P(A \cap A') = P(A'|A) \cdot P(A) \rightarrow$ Dependent Events
- $P(A \cap A') = P(A) \cdot P(A') \rightarrow$ Independents Events

where A and A' are two layers, h_m , of **H**. The hazard database **H** is completed when all potentially simultaneous events are identified or the combined probability can be considered negligible.

Vulnerabilities Analysis

The vulnerability analysis focuses on a specific electrical network, **N**.

The network **N** is a set of two layers, $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}]$, where **f** and **w** are layers that provide information related to buses and power lines, respectively. Regarding the type of features, **f** includes points (one per bus) and **w** lines (one per power line). Layers **f** and **w** include as attributes the technical characteristics of each system's element, represented by a feature in the layer.

The vulnerabilities can be characterized once the system, **N**, is defined. The vulnerability analysis involves three main steps: vulnerability identification, likelihood characterization, and impact calculations.

As for vulnerability identification, the process might involve the different system's stakeholders. This process results in a list of vulnerabilities v for each system's element.

Figure 1: Hazards Database

The presence of a vulnerability does not necessarily mean that the system will be compromised. Thus, the likelihood of being affected by a vulnerability varies depending on the hazard. Consequently, a specific vulnerability likelihood should be determined for each event included in the hazard database and for each vulnerability identified, h , $\mathbf{L}_{v,h}$. The vector $\mathbf{L}_{v,h}$ is a set of two tabular data, $\mathbf{L}_{v,h} = [\mathbf{l}-\mathbf{f}_{v,h}, \mathbf{l}-\mathbf{w}_{v,h}]$, for buses and power lines, respec-

tively. $\mathbf{I}\text{-f}_{v,h}$ and $\mathbf{I}\text{-w}_{v,h}$ have as many columns as hazards included in \mathbf{H} and as many rows as vulnerabilities per element.

The impact, \mathbf{I} , is set of two tabular data, $\mathbf{I} = [\mathbf{I}\text{-f}, \mathbf{I}\text{-w}]$, for buses and power lines, respectively. The layers $\mathbf{I}\text{-f}$ and $\mathbf{I}\text{-w}$ have as many rows as features included in \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{w} , respectively, a single column that provides the impact of each element is included. The impact that each element might have on the system can be quantified from technological, economic or social perspectives. This work defines the impact, \mathbf{I} , of an element through the amount of energy not supplied when the element is not in service. Thus, an Optimal Power Flow (OPF) approach is proposed to quantify the impact. The technical parameters required to perform the OPF are obtained from the attributes of \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{w} . The OPF objective function maximizes the energy supplied by the system, that is:

$$[\max] \sum_x \sum_t p_{load-x,t} \quad (1)$$

where $p_{load-x,t}$ is the power supplied from bus x at time t . Loads are assumed to be connected in a specific bus x . A bus x can be lost because of a specific issue in the bus itself or due to the loss of a power line that feeds it. Thus, the impact of each element, bus or power line, is determined by the difference between the total energy supplied when all elements are in service and the total energy supplied when the element is not in service.

Risk Assessment and Resilience analysis

After developing the hazard database, \mathbf{H} , for a specific region and evaluating the vulnerabilities, $\mathbf{L}_{v,h}$, and impact, \mathbf{I} , of a system, \mathbf{N} , the risk assessment methodology provides information about the criticality of each element and the global system resilience, as shown in Figure 2.

First, the power lines included in layer w of the network \mathbf{N} , are segmented, if required, to provide more detailed information. In this way, the network defined as $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}]$ turns into $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}\text{-q}]$ where q expresses the number of segments of each power line. The topology of $\mathbf{w}\text{-q}$ is the same as \mathbf{w} . However, more features are included to define the same system. Besides, the segment's length is included in the attributes of the layer.

Second, the extension of the hazard database is adjusted to the system's regions. As a result, the number of features included in each \mathbf{h}_m could be reduced and the computational time required is optimized.

Third, the intersections between the geospatial data of the system, \mathbf{N} , and the hazard database, \mathbf{H} , are evaluated for a certain season of the year. As a result, a new set of layers is created, $\mathbf{P}_h = [\rho\text{-f}_h, \rho\text{-w}\text{-q}_h]$. $\rho\text{-f}_h$ and $\rho\text{-w}\text{-q}_h$ include the same geospatial data and attributes as \mathbf{f} and $\mathbf{w}\text{-q}$, respectively, and add one attribute per hazard \mathbf{h}_m . The field of each new attribute is the hazard's name and the value is the element's probability of being affected by hazard, \mathbf{h}_m . The probability is taken from hazard's attributes.

Fourth, the tabular data obtained from the vulnerability analysis, $\mathbf{L}_{v,h}$ and \mathbf{I} , are combined to the geospatial data of \mathbf{P}_h through each element's name. The energy at risk in

each bus and power line is determined as follows:

$$\mathbf{r}\text{-f} = \sum_h \sum_v \rho\text{-f}_h \cdot \mathbf{I}\text{-f}_{v,h} \cdot \mathbf{I}\text{-f} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{r}\text{-w}\text{-q} = \sum_h \sum_v \rho\text{-w}\text{-q}_h \cdot \mathbf{I}\text{-w}_{v,h} \cdot \mathbf{I}\text{-w} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{s}_l}{\mathbf{I}} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{s}_l is a vector of the segment's length and \mathbf{I} the power line's total length. This factor is considered because of the power lines segmentation performed in the first stage. $\mathbf{r}\text{-f}$ and $\mathbf{r}\text{-w}\text{-q}$ are two layers included in the set of layers \mathbf{R} . Their topology is the same as \mathbf{N} . However, as attributes, the layers provide the amount of energy at risk.

Finally, a resilience index, \mathcal{R} , for the whole system is determined based on the total energy risked and the aggregated impact as follows:

$$R_T = \sum \mathbf{r}\text{-f} + \sum \mathbf{r}\text{-w}\text{-q} \quad (4)$$

$$I_T = \sum \mathbf{I}\text{-f} + \sum \mathbf{I}\text{-w} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{R} = \frac{R_T}{I_T} \quad (6)$$

where R_T is the total energy at risk in the system. R_T is obtained by summing the amount of energy at risk in each element provided from the attributes of \mathbf{R} . In turn, I_T is the sum of the partial impacts identified in the system. I_T is obtained by summing the partial impacts provided from the attributes of \mathbf{I} . As a result, \mathcal{R} is a numerical index that determines the global system's resilience. This variable enables the comparison of different systems.

CASE STUDY

This section presents a simplified case study to validate the presented resilience analysis. The case study considers a rural area's network located in Catalonia, Spain's north-east region. Figure 3 - g) shows the network's topology. The size of the buses in the Figure is proportional to the associated demand, which has been estimated based on the transformer's size and varies from 320 kW to 8 kW. The largest bus in the northwest is the one with the highest consumption and the only one connected to the external grid. As for the power lines, the system is composed mainly of overhead power lines. However, some underground power lines are included.

This case study will evaluate the impact of the presence of high-dense vegetation on the system's resilience.

The resilience evaluation considers five different hazards. First, three simple hazards are considered: wildfires \mathbf{h}_1 , heatwaves \mathbf{h}_2 and wind gusts \mathbf{h}_3 . Their probability of occurrence is shown in Figure 3 - a) to c). The heatwave is not a hazard for the system by itself but, combined with others can increase the probability of suffering damage. In that context, three different combined hazards are determined:

1. $\mathbf{h}_4: \mathbf{h}_2 + \mathbf{h}_1 \rightarrow$ Dep. Events [Figure 3 - d]
2. $\mathbf{h}_5: \mathbf{h}_3 + \mathbf{h}_1 \rightarrow$ Indep. Events [Figure 3 - e]
3. $\mathbf{h}_6: \mathbf{h}_2 + \mathbf{h}_1 + \mathbf{h}_3 \rightarrow$ Dep. Events + Indep. Events [Figure 3 - g]

Regarding the vulnerabilities, the Green Leaf Index (GLI) determines the likelihood of being affected by high-dense vegetation. The index measures the vegetation density

Figure 2: Risk Assessment and Resilience Analysis

based on the RGB composition of the aerial images [10]. The likelihood is set to 0 for buses and underground power lines, as those elements are not vulnerable because of vegetation. Figure 3 - h) illustrates the likelihood of being impacted by vegetation density. The impact, as previously mentioned, has been determined through an OPF methodology. Figure 3 - i) shows the impact of each element. Elements situated closer to the external grid connection exhibit a higher impact on the system, as this proximity increases the number of unsupplied loads.

Finally, hazards and vulnerabilities are combined to determine the amount of power at risk in each element. Figure 3 - j) shows that those overhead power lines close to the external grid connection are the ones with higher power at risk. The resilience index obtained is 99.75 %. Thus, the impact of the single vulnerability on the system's resilience, considering a reduced hazard database, is less than 0.5 %.

CONCLUSIONS

Resilience has concluded as a very complex topic that requires coordination between the different stakeholders of the system. First, the hazard database needs to be constantly updated and extended. Second, ongoing analysis of the network's vulnerabilities is essential to identify emerging vulnerabilities and address previously mitigated

ones. As a result, resilience studies require a large amount of data. In that context, this work identified the potential of geospatial data to address the system's resilience.

The proposed methodology allows the management of many hazards and the potential combinations between them. The vulnerability analysis is a complex stage. This work proposes a qualitative method to identify the vulnerabilities of the system and their likelihood of impacting when a specific hazard occurs. In turn, an OPF approach is proposed to estimate the impact of each network's element. However, other methods are compatible with the risk assessment and resilience analysis.

The developed methodology allows the identification of the most critical elements or parts of the network. The global resilience index provides information about how the identified vulnerabilities might affect the system considering the hazards included in the database. This index is useful to evaluate the global impact of various mitigation actions.

MISCELLANEOUS

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Figure 3: Case Study: a) h_1 , b) h_2 , c) h_3 , d) h_4 , e) h_5 , f) h_6 , g) N, h) $L_{v,h}$, i) I, j) R

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